

Topic	Item	Checklist item description	Reported on Line
Title	1	The diagnosis or intervention of primary focus followed by the words "case report"	Page 1
Key Words	2	2 to 5 key words that identify diagnoses or interventions in this case report, including "case report" ...	Page 2
Abstract (no references)	3a	Introduction: What is unique about this case and what does it add to the scientific literature?	Page 3
	3b	Main symptoms and/or important clinical findings	Page 3,4
	3c	The main diagnoses, therapeutic interventions, and outcomes	Page 3,4,5
	3d	Conclusion—What is the main "take-away" lesson(s) from this case?	Page 6
Introduction	4	One or two paragraphs summarizing why this case is unique (may include references)	Page 5,6
Patient Information	5a	De-identified patient specific information	Page 3,4
	5b	Primary concerns and symptoms of the patient	Page 3,4
	5c	Medical, family, and psycho-social history including relevant genetic information	Page 3,4
	5d	Relevant past interventions with outcomes	Page 3,4
	6	Describe significant physical examination (PE) and important clinical findings.	Page 4,5
Clinical Findings	7	Historical and current information from this episode of care organized as a timeline	Page 4,5,6
Timeline	8a	Diagnostic testing (such as PE, laboratory testing, imaging, surveys)	Not Applicable
Diagnostic Assessment	8b	Diagnostic challenges (such as access to testing, financial, or cultural)	Not Applicable
	8c	Diagnosis (including other diagnoses considered)	Page 4,5
	8d	Prognosis (such as staging in oncology) where applicable	Not Applicable
	9a	Types of therapeutic intervention (such as pharmacologic, surgical, preventive, self-care)	Not Applicable
Therapeutic Intervention	9b	Administration of therapeutic intervention (such as dosage, strength, duration)	Not Applicable
	9c	Changes in therapeutic intervention (with rationale)	Not Applicable
	10a	Clinician and patient-assessed outcomes (if available)	Page 4,5
Follow-up and Outcomes	10b	Important follow-up diagnostic and other test results	Not Applicable
	10c	Intervention adherence and tolerability (How was this assessed?)	Not Applicable
	10d	Adverse and unanticipated events	Not Applicable
	11a	A scientific discussion of the strengths AND limitations associated with this case report	Page 5,6
Discussion	11b	Discussion of the relevant medical literature with references	Page 5,6
	11c	The scientific rationale for any conclusions (including assessment of possible causes)	Page 5,6
	11d	The primary "take-away" lessons of this case report (without references) in a one paragraph conclusion	Page 6
	12	The patient should share their perspective in one to two paragraphs on the treatment(s) they received	Not Applicable
Patient Perspective	13	Did the patient give informed consent? Please provide if requested	Not Applicable
Informed Consent			Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>